

Extraction of Dye from Coconut Husk (*Cocos Nucifera*) and Its Effect on Cotton Fabric Extract

Olufunmilayo Olasunbo Braide

*Department of Home Science and Management, College of Food Science and Human Ecology,
Federal University of Agriculture, Abeokuta, Ogun, Nigeria*

Oladoyin Jamiu Labode

*Department of Home Science and Management, College of Food Science and Human Ecology,
Federal University of Agriculture, Abeokuta, Ogun, Nigeria*

Muti Olasunkanmi Amuda

*Department of Pure and Applied Chemistry, Ladoke Akintola University of Technology,
Ogbomoso, Oyo state, Nigeria*

Oluwayemisi Oluwafunmilayo Bolarin

*Department of Home Science and Management, College of Food Science and Human Ecology,
Federal University of Agriculture, Abeokuta, Ogun, Nigeria*

Article History:

Received: 16.01.2025 Revised: 10.03.2025 Accepted: 28.03.2025 Published: 03.04.2025

Abstract

This study examined the extraction of dye from coconut husk and its effects on colouring of cotton fabric. Three different solvents were used in the extraction process namely methanol, ethanol, and acetone. The ethanol fraction gave the highest yield of extraction ranging from (E₃) 40.3%, (E₂) 24.3%, (E₁) 12.2% over acetone with (A₃) 37.2%, (A₂) 22.5%, (A₁) 11.2% and methanol with (M₃) 30.3%, (M₂) 18.1%, (M₁) 9.15% respectively. The extract was found to be slightly acidic as the pH of the dye extracted ranges from (A₂) 4.6 to (E₃) 50. The dye extracted exhibits exceptional light and wash fastness using allum (aluminium sulfate) as mordant. The dyeing process also involves the interaction between the dye molecules and cotton fabric, illustrating the concept of absorption, adsorption and diffusion which makes it significant. The extracted dye can be used to create unique, sustainable textiles with potential applications in fashion, upholstery and other industries.

Keywords: Dye, extraction, ethanol, cotton fabric.

Suggested citation: Braide, O.O., Labode, O.J., Amuda, M.O., & Bolarin, O.O. (2025). Extraction of Dye from Coconut Husk (*Cocos Nucifera*) and Its Effect on Cotton Fabric Extract. *European Journal of Theoretical and Applied Sciences*, 3(2), 383-394. [https://doi.org/10.59324/ejtas.2025.3\(2\).33](https://doi.org/10.59324/ejtas.2025.3(2).33)

Introduction

Dyes are coloured substance which are basically used for colouring. Natural dyes are colours generated from plant sources (Ragab, Hassabo, & Othman, 2022). From time immemorial, natural dyes were commonly employed to colour

products in various sectors, including textile, leather, pulp, paper, and plastics (Helmy, 2020). These plants materials and wastes are harmless and biodegradable, which make them safe. (Chilukoti, Venkatesh, & Chandana, 2019; Broadbent, 2001).

Natural dyes are organic compounds, as the name implies, are generated from natural materials (Patel, 2011). The use of natural dyes is seen to be a preferable to industries when compared with synthetic dye (Ebrahim, et al., 2022; AlAshkar, & Hassabo, 2021). Plants have historically been utilized to derive the bulk of natural colours (Ahmed, Eltahir, & Saeed, 2018). The majority of natural colouring supplies include roots, leaves, stems, bark, wood shavings, flowers, fruits, rinds, hulls, husks, and other plant components. (Muthu, 2018; Kasiri, & Safapour, 2014).

Cocos nucifera, or more commonly known as the coconut, is a member of the Arecaceae family (palm family) (Imo, et al., 2018). The coconut is a major crop in Malaysia with a total plantation acreage of approximately 85,000 hectares with each hectare being able to produce up to 15,000 coconuts (Tan, Ahmad, & Hameed, 2008).

The demand for coconut is increasing annually and these results in an accumulation of coconut waste as coconut husk. Coconut husk is composed of 30% fiber and 70% pith. It is also high in cellulose (41%), lignin (40%), and phenolic content (Israel, et al., 2011). The high lignin content contributes to the elasticity and durability of coconut fiber. It also makes the coconut fiber resistant to rotting.

In addition, coconut husk also contains tannin and potassium. The coconut husk consists of the endocarp, mesocarp, and exocarp which make up about 30-35% of the whole coconut (Tan, Ahmad, & Hameed, 2008). It is estimated that 5280 kg of dry coconut husk is produced per hectare every year which is significant and (Rodiah, et al., 2018) there is a dire need to find a way to manage the waste. One approach is to add value to the waste by utilizing the coconut husk as a dye substance for colouring cotton fabric. Coconut husk waste is cheap, non-toxic, efficient, and readily available. Thus, the use of coconut waste as a natural dye can reduce the cost of waste management and help prevent environmental pollution. Therefore, this study highlights the effects of the application of dye extracted from coconut husk on cotton fabric in the textile industry.

Materials and Methods

Study Area

The study was carried out at Federal University of Agriculture, Abeokuta at the Department of Home Science and Management Textile Laboratory and Analytical Laboratory of Food Science and Technology of the Department of Food Science and Technology.

Material under Study (Coconut Husk)

Coconut husk is the main plant waste used for the extraction of dye for this study. *Cocos nucifera*, is commonly known as the coconut as show in figure 1, is a member of the Arecaceae family (palm family) (Imo, et al., 2018). It composed of 30% fiber and 70% pith (Israel, et al., 2011). coconut husk also contains potassium. The coconut husk consists of the endocarp, mesocarp, and exocarp which make up about 30-35% of the whole coconut (Tan, Ahmad, & Hameed, 2008). It is estimated that 5280 kg of dry coconut husk is produced per hectare every year which is significant and (Rodiah, et al., 2018) there is a dire need to find a way to manage the waste.

Figure 1. Coconut Husk

The coconut husk commonly found in Nigeria was purchased from Eleweran market, Abeokuta in Ogun State. The Nuts of coconut (*Cocos*

nucifera) were purchased and the husk (bark of coconut fruit) was removed as a waste shredded into coir (powder) form and used for the study as shown figure 2. The dried husk of coconut was washed with distilled water, dried at room temperature, chopped into smaller pieces separated into different particle sizes and the measured quantities of pulverized samples were fed into the muslin bag as shown in figure 3 and prepared for extraction.

Figure 2. Coconut Husk Blend

Reagents and Apparatus Used for the Extraction

1. Coconut husks sourced from Eleweran market, Ogun State.
2. Solvents such as Acetone (CH_3COCH_3) sourced from Rivaan Pharmachem Private
3. Limited, Ethanol ($\text{CH}_3\text{CH}_2\text{OH}$) sourced from Shandong Jinta Machinery Group CO, Ltd, and Methanol (CH_3OH) sourced from Methanex Corporation Vancouver, Canada;
4. Cotton fabrics (100% white) sourced from Itoku market, Ogun State.
5. Muslin cloth: is a plain-woven cotton fabric made in various weights.
6. Volumetric flask (100ml/ 500ml),.
7. Beakers of varying sizes,

8. Graduated Measuring Cylinder of volume size 10, 20, 25 and 100ml.
9. Soxhlet extractor.
10. Heating Mantle:
11. Weighing balance scale:
12. Pots: a cylindrical container, typically metal, used for cooking.
13. Water Bath.
14. Rotary Evaporator.
15. Thermometer.
16. Colourimeter.
17. Digital pH meter.

Figure 3. Muslin Cloth Filled with Measured Blended Husk Coir Fixed in Thimble

Extraction of Dye from Coconut Husk

The Soxhlet extractor was used to extract colour from coconut husk, with solvents such as acetone, ethanol, and methanol. Different grams ranging from 10g, 20g, and 30g of coconut husk powder was weighed in a muslin cloth. The muslin cloth was put in the thimble and fix the thimble in the siphon tube. The empty container was label. The apparatus was adjusted with water inlet connected in and out of the condenser, allowing it to pass through from below to top of the condenser to avoid air bubbles and over-floating. After filling solvent into the conical flask, the heating mantle temperature ranges from 40-60°C, the siphon tube would first siphon, then fill half of the tube and solvent would drop back into the conical flask. The sample was then from thimble, the muslin cloth sample and conical flask was kept

to dry in room temperature for 24 hours. When the smell of sample was free, it means it has been dried. Second extraction process with different experimental run was repeated with different samples, solvents and at different times. The set-up was put in a water bath with a continuous boiling temperature of 60°C and the solvent was heated to reflux. Different extraction time ranging from 30mins., 60min., and 90min. respectively, totaling nine times. The same technique was followed for each solvent, as the dye generated did not exhibit the predicted deep colour cloth staining capacity during the first phases of the experiment.

Determination of Percentage Yield of Dye Extracted from Coconut Husk

The extracted dye yield was measured by determining the solvent's efficiency to specific components from the original material (Murugan, & Parimelazhangam, 2022). This was defined as the amount of extract recovered in mass compared to the initial amount of the whole plant. This was expressed in percentage (Ey %).

The equation used for calculation of the extracted dye yield is

$$Ey(\%) = \frac{W_1 - W_2}{W_2} \quad (1)$$

Determination of the pH Value of the Extracted Dye

Most natural dyes are sensitive to pH changes and will produce different colors depending on the acidity or alkalinity of the dye bath. The pH of the extract was determined using a handheld pH meter. The extracted dyes were cooled to room temperature before analysis. The pH meter was put in the solvent and turn on, distilled water is needed for accurate calibration.

Evaluation of the Quality Characteristics of Extracted Dye

Conventional mordanting technique used by Mahangade *et al.*, (2009) was adopted for the extracted dye from coconut husk (*cocos nucifera.L*) which was utilized to determine the quality

characteristics of extracted dye for the coloration of cotton fabric. The conventional mordanting technique was explored to study the effect on the colour strength and fastness properties of the dyed samples.

Scouring and Mordanting of Fabric

The cotton fabric was washed in order to remove all the impurities and starch present in the fabric and the fabric was later dried at room temperature (Swani, Saini, & Gupta, 2012). In order to charge the cotton fabric (substrate) to be dyed, potassium Aluminum Sulphate which is locally known as alum, cooking salt, vinegar, or baking soda can either be used for the treatment. One-liter (1litter) of water was filled in a pot; 1 tablespoon (1 Tb) alum and cream of tartar were added to it plus the substrate at 40°C with constant stirring and simmered for 20 minutes. The substrate (fabric) was allowed to cool off and soaked in the mordant solution overnight. Allum (aluminum sulfate) was used as mordant in the study because it occurs naturally in nature and some plants contains allum.

Dyeing of Fabric

5ml of the concentrated solvent dye extract was used for each dyeing process. The proportion of the fabric to be dyed with the dye extract were constant in all the operations. The measurement of the fabric was 4cm by 4cm. 5ml of the liquid dye was measured into a container and the fabric was submerged into the container and the fabric was stirred approximately for 20 minutes respectively. The dyed fabric was removed and aired for oxidation to take place for 5minutes. It was rinsed separately in running water and dried under room temperature.

Results

Dye Extract Percentage Yield

It was observed that the ethanol fraction with 500ml solvent (E₃) used gave the highest yield with 40.3% at 60°C in 90mins. Acetone fraction with 500ml solvent used (A₃) gave 37.2% at 60°C in 90mins, which was followed by methanol fraction with 500ml solvent used (M₃) with 30.3% at 60°C in 90mins. Other fractions such as ethanol fractions with 300ml solvent used (E₂), gave 24.3% at 60°C in 60mins, acetone

fraction with 300ml (A₂) gave 22.5% at 60°C in 60mins, methanol fraction with 300ml(M₂) gave 18.1% yield at 60°C in 60mins. Another Ethanol fraction with 150ml solvent used (E₁) gave 12.2% yield with 60°C in 30mins., while Acetone

fraction with 150ml solvent (A₁) gave 11.2% yield at 60°C in 30mins., methanol fraction with 150ml solvent used (M₁) gave the lowest yield of 9.15% at 60°C in 30mins.

Table 1. Dye Extraction Percentage (%) Yield from Coconut Husk

S/n	Sample	Solvent used	Solvent Volume (ml)	Coconut Husk (g)	Weight of husk after extraction (g)	Average Extracted Dye yield (%)	Temperature (°c)	Time (m)
1	A ₁	Acetone	150	10	8.88	11.2	60°c	30
2	E ₁	Ethanol	150	10	8.78	12.2	60°c	30
3	M ₁	Methanol	150	10	9.09	9.15	60°c	30
4	A ₂	Acetone	300	20	15.5	22.5	60°c	60
5	E ₂	Ethanol	300	20	15.14	24.3	60°c	60
6	M ₂	Methanol	300	20	16.38	18.1	60°c	60
7	A ₃	Acetone	500	30	18.85	37.2	60°c	90
8	E ₃	Ethanol	500	30	17.9	40.3	60°c	90
9	M ₃	Methanol	500	30	20.9	30.3	60°c	90

Note: A = Acetone, E = Ethanol, M = Methanol

pH Value of Extracted Dye Samples

The pH value of the extracted dyes from coconut husk was presented in table 2 below. The methanol solvent (M₃) of 500ml volume of solvent with 30g of coconut husk had the highest

pH value of 5.0 and ethanol solvent (E₂) of 300ml volume of solvent with 20g of coconut husk had the lowest pH value of 4.7. This result was recorded in accordance with the acidic range of dye for extraction as it falls within the slightly acidic range on the pH table.

Table 2. pH of Dye Extract of Coconut Husk Dust Using Soxhlet Extraction Method

S/No	Sample	Solvent	Volume of solvent (ml)	Amount of particle (g)	pH of dye extract
1	A ₁	Acetone	150	10	4.8
2	E ₁	Ethanol	150	10	4.9
3	M ₁	Methanol	150	10	4.9
4	A ₂	Acetone	300	20	4.6
5	E ₂	Ethanol	300	20	4.7
6	M ₂	Methanol	300	20	4.9
7	A ₃	Acetone	500	30	4.8
8	E ₃	Ethanol	500	30	5.0
9	M ₃	Methanol	500	30	4.9

Note: A = Acetone, E = Ethanol, M = Methanol.

Quality Characteristics of Dye Extracted

Light Fastness of dye extract on cotton fabrics with No-Mordant

The quality characteristics of extracted dye from coconut was determined according to blue scale. The colour parameters result of the light fastness

properties of dyed cotton fabric with No mordant were presented in the table below. However, the table reveals the whiteness to blackness (L), greenness to redness (a), and blueness to yellowness (b) for each dyed fabric samples. The colour parameters of Sample E₃ (72.1, 6.4, 12.3) shows a lighter color compared

to E₁ (70.2, 4.8, 12.0) which is close in lighter shade of colour yield and colour parameters than other samples like A₁ (53.9, 12.1, 2.5); sample E₂ (72.0, 6.0, 12.1) and sample A₂ (54.3, 12.1, 2.7); samples E₃ (72.1, 6.4, 12.3) and sample A₃ (56.3, 12.4, 2.8). However, the result showed that Ethanol fraction (E₃) has the highest colour parameters value while A₁ has the lowest colour parameters for light fastness with no-mordant. E₃ has the highest ΔE_{nm} of 73.4 while A₁ has the lowest ΔE_n 55.3 (Table 3 – Appendix)

Light Fastness properties of dye extract from coconut husk on cotton fabrics with alum (Aluminum sulfate)

Alum (Alluminium sulfate) was used as the mordant for testing lightfast properties of extracted dye from coconut husk on cotton fabric which is presented in table 4 below. These table reveals the whiteness to blackness (L), greenness to redness (a), and blueness to yellowness (b) of each dyed fabric sample. The colour parameters value of Sample M₁ (68.8, -0.2, 18.0) which shows the lightest shade of colour yield and colour parameters than sample A₁ (60.9, 10.5, 20.4); samples E₂ (72.0, 6.0, 12.1) and sample A₂ (54.3, 12.1, 2.7); samples E₃ (72.1, 6.4, 12.3) and sample A₃ (56.3, 12.4, 2.8). However, the result showed that Ethanol (E₃) has the highest colour parameters value while A₁ has the lowest Lab value for light fastness no mordant. Furthermore, (M₃) ΔE_{al} indicates 73.1 which shows the highest yield while (A₁) ΔE_{al} indicates 65.1 which is the least dye yield (Table 4 – Appendix).

Wash Fastness dye extract on cotton fabrics with no mordant.

The dyed cotton fabric samples that was not mordanted was tested for wash fastness while the results of wash fastness properties of dye extract from coconut husk on cotton fabrics were presented in Table 11. It showed that when cotton were dyed without mordant, colour parameters of E₃ (72.2, 5.3, 11.1) was observed which indicates the highest wash fastness while colour parameters of A₁ (55.0, 10.8, 24.8) indicates the lowest range of fabric. However, E₃ indicates 73.2 as the highest value of ΔE_{bs} while

A₁ indicates 61.3 which is the lowest values of ΔE_{bs} (Table 5 – Appendix).

Wash Fastness of dye extract on cotton fabrics Mordanted with Alum

The dyed cotton fabric samples that was mordanted with allum was tested for wash fastness while the results of wash fastness properties of dye extract from coconut husk on cotton fabrics was presented above in Table 6. The result showed that when cotton were dyed with alum, colour parameters of M₃ (77.3, -2.0, 2.1) was observed which indicates the highest wash fastness while colour parameters of A₁ (59.2, 11.3, 22.0) indicates the lowest range of fabric. However, M₃ indicates 77.4 as the highest value of ΔE_{al} while A₁ indicates 64.2 which is the lowest values of ΔE_{a} (Table 6 – Appendix).

Discussion

The ethanol fraction of “dye extracted from coconut husk (*Cocos nucifera*)”, was found to have the highest yield of the dye pigment with (E₃) 40.3%, (E₂) 24.3%, (E₁) 12.2% over acetone with (A₃) 37.2%, (A₂) 22.5%, (A₁) 11.2% and methanol with (M₃) 30.3%, (M₂) 18.1%, (M₁) 9.15% respectively, these could be as a result of the solubility of dye pigment extracted from the husk because most plant color pigments are water soluble, but the chlorophylls are hydrophobic and dissolve best in hydrophobic solvents. Ethanol can be able to dissolve both hydrophobic and hydrophilic pigments.

Ethanol is sometimes classified as a soluble hydrocarbon. (E₃) proves to be the most efficient to obtain highest extract of dye yield using soxhlet extraction method, these support the claim that soxhlet extraction is a very efficient form of extracting color from solid materials (Vankar, Shanker, & Wijayapala, 2009). Although temperature could be the main factor which affects the extraction efficiency of dye from natural plant (Nwonye, & Priscilla, 2017).

Also, the importance of pH is to ensure that the dye adheres to the fabric and achieve the desired color intensity, pH is measure of relative amount of free hydrogen and hydroxyl ion in a solution. The range goes from 0-14, with 7 being neutral. pH of less than 7 indicates acidity, the extracted

dye yield resulting from coconut husk were found to be slightly acidic, which is the characteristic of natural dyes (Osabohien, 2014). The result also reveals that when the heat of the solvent comes in contact with husk coir, the extracting power becomes more efficient with the pH values ranging from (E₃) 5.0 to (A₂) 4.7 as shown in table 2.

The colourimeter of the extracted dye samples from the coconut husk were evaluated which gave colour parameter of Light fastness quality characteristics of mordanted and no-mordant fabric dyed with extracted dyes shown in table 3 and the colour parameters values of wash fastness quality characteristics of mordanted and no-mordant fabric dyed with extracted dye from coconut husk seen in table 4, the absorption obtained from the analysis showed evidence of colour composites which the dyed cotton fabrics was able to absorb using alum as mordant, The mordanted fabrics showed better light and wash fastness properties compared to the unmordanted fabrics. Delta E (ΔE) provides a value indicating the overall difference between two colours (Torres, et al., 2015). i.e. which colour is lighter/darker, redder/greener, more blue/more yellow in order to understand the difference in colour.

Conclusion

It has been established from the foregoing that dye extracted from coconut husk has good affinity to bind with cotton fabric to produce an appealing colour. The experimentation and utilization of plant waste from coconut husk will be helpful for waste management as well as preparation of dye as a value added product for textile production as the husk is a rich source of natural pigments. The dyeing process also involves the interaction between the dye molecules and cotton fabric, illustrating the concept of absorption, adsorption and diffusion which makes it significant. The extracted dye can be used to create unique, sustainable textiles with potential applications in fashion, upholstery and other industries.

Conflict of Interest

The authors declares that there is no conflict of interest in this research, all authors in this

manuscript contributed to the research work immensely.

References

- Ahmed, M. A., Eltahir, Y. A., & Saced, H. A. M. (2018). Eco-friendly utilization of banana plant extract for dyeing of textile materials and related purposes. *International Journal of Recent Scientific Research*, 9(5), 26465-26473.
- AlAshkar, A., & Hassabo, A. G. (2021). Recent use of natural animal dyes in various fields. *Journal of Textiles, Coloration and Polymer Science*, 18(2), 191-210.
- Broadbent, A. D. (2001). *Basic principles of textile coloration*. Society of Dyers and Colourists.
- Chilukoti, G. R., Venkatesh, B., & Chandana, V. S. (2019). Optimisation of dyeing and mordanting parameters on cotton fabrics treated with *Allium cepa* as a natural dye source. *Journal of the Textile Association*, 80(5), 333-339.
- Ebrahim, S. A., Mosaad, M. M., Othman, H., & Hassabo, A. G. (2022). A valuable observation of eco-friendly natural dyes for valuable utilisation in the textile industry. *Journal of Textiles, Coloration and Polymer Science*, 19(1), 25-37.
- Helmy, H. M. (2020). Extraction approaches of natural dyes for textile coloration. *Journal of Textiles, Coloration and Polymer Science*, 17(2), 65-76.
- Imo, C., Ezaonu, C. S., Imo, N. G., & Anigbo, C. J. (2018). Proximate, mineral and phytochemical composition of *Cocos nucifera* nut. *Asian Journal of Biochemistry*, 13(1), 9-14.
- Israel, A. U., Ogali, R. E., Akaranta, O., & Obot, I. B. (2011). Extraction and characterization of coconut (*Cocos nucifera* L.) coir dust. *Songklanakarin Journal of Science and Technology*, 33(6), 717-724.
- Kasiri, M. B., & Safapour, S. (2014). Natural dyes and antimicrobials for green treatment of textiles. *Environmental Chemistry Letters*, 12(1), 1-13. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10311-013-0436-6>

- Mahangade, R. R., Varadarajan, P. V., Verma, J. K., & Bosco, H. (2009). New dyeing technique for enhancing colour strength and fastness properties of cotton fabric dyed with natural dye. *Indian Journal of Fibre & Textile Research*, 34(3), 279-282.
- Murugan, R., & Parimelazhangan, T. (2022). Comparative evaluation of different extraction methods for antioxidants and anti-inflammatory properties. *Journal of Chemical Society of Nigeria*, 47(3), 625-640.
- Muthu, S. S. (Ed.). (2018). *Textile science and clothing technology*. Springer.
- Nwonye, N. U., & Priscilla, N. E. (2017). Extraction and utilization of natural dye extract from Guinea corn leaf. *International Journal of Development Strategies in Humanities, Management and Social Sciences*, 7(1).
- Osabohien, E. (2014). Extraction and application of dyestuffs from the leaves of guinea corn and onion skin. *International Journal of Biological and Chemical Sciences*, 8(2), 811-819. <https://doi.org/10.4314/ijbcs.v8i2.41>
- Patel, B. H. (2011). Natural dyes. In *Handbook of Textile and Industrial Dyeing* (Vol. 1, pp. 395-424). Woodhead Publishing.
- Ragab, M. M., Hassabo, A. G., & Othman, H. A. (2022). An overview of natural dyes extraction techniques for valuable utilization on textile fabrics. *Journal of Textiles, Coloration and Polymer Science*, 19(2).
- Rodiah, M. H., Nur-Asma-Fhadhila, Z., Kawasaki, N., Noor-Asiah, H., & Aziah, M. Y. (2018). Antioxidant activity of natural pigment from husk of coconut. *Pertanika Journal of Tropical Agricultural Science*, 41(1), 441-452.
- Swani, C., Saini, S., & Gupta, V. B. (2012). A study on green dyeing of cotton with ethanolic extract of *Sesbania aculeata*. *Universal Journal of Environmental Research and Technology*, 2(2), 38-47.
- Tan, I. A. W., Ahmad, A. L., & Hameed, B. H. (2008). Preparation of activated carbon from coconut husk: Optimization study on removal of 2,4,6-trichlorophenol using response surface methodology. *Journal of Hazardous Materials*, 153(1-2), 709-717. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jhazmat.2007.09.014>
- Torres, M. V., Guzmán, J. M., Tártara, L., Vázquez, H., Coradin, T., & Desimone, M. F. (2015). Dye–collagen interaction: Mechanisms, kinetics, and thermodynamic analysis. *RSC Advances*, 5(70), 57395-57404. <https://doi.org/10.1039/C5RA09360A>
- Vankar, P. S., Shanker, R., & Wijayapala, S. (2009). Dyeing of cotton, wool and silk with extract of *Allium cepa*. *Pigment & Resin Technology*, 38(4), 242-247. <https://doi.org/10.1108/03699420910973329>

Appendix

Table 3. Color Parameters of Light Fastness for Dyed Cotton Fabric with No Mordant

S/N	Solvent	Amount of Particle (g)	Light Image	fastness	L ₁	a ₁	b ₁	L ₂	a ₂	b ₂	L ₃	a ₃	b ₃	L _{nm}	a _{nm}	b _{nm}	ΔEnm
1	A ₁	10			54.0	12.2	2.6	53.9	12.1	2.5	53.8	12.0	2.4	53.9	12.1	2.5	55.3
2	E ₁	10			70.2	4.8	12.0	70.1	4.7	11.9	70.3	4.9	12.1	70.2	4.8	12.0	71.4
3	M ₁	10			68.1	10.7	20.8	67.9	10.5	20.4	68.0	10.6	20.7	68.0	10.6	20.7	71.9
4	A ₂	20			54.4	12.2	2.8	54.3	12.1	2.7	54.2	12.0	2.6	54.3	12.1	2.7	55.7
5	E ₂	20			72.0	6.0	12.1	71.9	5.9	12.0	72.1	6.1	12.2	72.0	6.0	12.1	73.3
6	M ₂	20			68.9	11.3	21.0	68.7	11.1	20.8	68.8	11.2	20.9	68.8	11.2	20.9	72.8
7	A ₃	30			56.4	12.5	2.9	56.3	12.4	2.8	56.2	12.3	2.7	56.3	12.4	2.8	57.7
8	E ₃	30			72.1	6.4	12.3	72.0	6.3	12.2	72.2	6.5	12.4	72.1	6.4	12.3	73.4
9	M ₃	30			70.0	11.4	21.0	68.8	11.2	20.8	68.9	11.5	21.1	68.9	11.5	21.1	73.0

Note: A = Acetone, E= Ethanol, M= Methanol, nm = no mordant, L = whiteness to blackness, a = greenness to redness, b = blueness to yellowness, L_{nm} = whiteness to blackness no mordant, a_{nm} = greenness to redness no mordant, b_{nm} = blueness to yellowness no mordant, ΔEnm = Delta E no mordant

Table 4. Color Parameters Light Fastness Value of Dyed Cotton Fabric Mordanted with Allum (Aluminum sulfate)

S/N	Solvent	Amount of Particle (g)	Light fastness Image	L ₁	a ₁	b ₁	L ₂	a ₂	b ₂	L ₃	a ₃	b ₃	L _{al}	a _{al}	b _{al}	ΔEal
1	A1	10		61.0	10.6	20.5	60.9	10.5	20.4	60.8	10.4	20.3	60.9	10.5	20.4	65.1
2	E1	10		63.4	2.0	22.7	63.2	1.9	22.6	63.5	2.1	22.8	63.4	2.0	22.7	67.4
3	M1	10		68.9	-0.3	18.1	68.7	-0.1	17.9	68.8	-0.2	18.0	68.8	-0.2	18.0	71.1
4	A2	20		61.4	12.2	22.9	61.2	12.0	22.9	61.3	12.1	22.8	61.3	12.1	22.8	66.5
5	E2	20		64.1	2.2	24.1	64.0	2.1	24.0	64.2	2.3	24.2	64.1	2.2	24.1	68.5
6	M2	20		70.3	-0.5	20.0	70.1	-0.3	19.8	70.2	-0.4	19.9	70.2	-0.4	19.9	73.0
7	A3	30		61.5	12.3	24.4	61.4	12.2	24.3	61.3	12.1	24.2	61.4	12.2	24.3	67.2
8	E3	30		65.3	2.2	24.3	65.2	2.1	24.2	65.4	2.3	24.4	65.3	2.2	24.3	69.7
9	M3	30		70.4	-0.6	20.0	70.2	-0.4	19.8	70.3	-0.5	19.9	70.3	-0.5	19.9	73.1

Note: A = Acetone, E= Ethanol, M= Methanol, al = alum L = whiteness to blackness, a = greenness to redness, b = blueness to yellowness, L_{al} = whiteness to blackness alum, a_{al} = greenness to redness alum, b_{al} = blueness to yellowness alum, ΔEal = Delta E alum.

Table 5. Color Parameters Value for Wash Fastness of Dyed Cotton Fabric with No-Mordant

S/N	Solvent	Wash fastness Image	L ₁	a ₁	b ₁	L ₂	a ₂	b ₂	L ₃	a ₃	b ₃	L _{nm}	a _{nm}	b _{nm}	ΔE _{nm}
1	A1		55.1	10.9	24.9	54.9	10.7	24.7	55.0	10.8	24.8	55.0	10.8	24.8	61.3
2	E1		72.0	5.0	11.0	71.9	4.9	10.9	72.1	5.1	11.1	72.0	5.0	11.0	73.0
3	M1		67.9	8.0	20.2	68.0	8.1	20.3	67.8	7.9	20.1	67.9	8.0	20.2	71.3
4	A2		55.2	11.8	24.9	55.3	11.8	25.0	55.1	11.7	25.0	55.2	11.8	24.9	61.7
5	E2		72.1	5.2	11.1	72.0	5.1	11.0	72.2	5.3	11.2	72.2	5.2	11.1	73.2
6	M2		68.0	8.2	20.2	68.1	8.3	20.3	67.9	8.1	20.1	68.0	8.2	20.2	71.4
7	A3		55.4	12.0	25.0	55.3	11.9	24.9	55.2	11.8	24.8	55.3	11.9	24.9	61.8
8	E3		72.2	5.3	11.1	72.1	5.2	11.0	72.3	5.4	11.2	72.2	5.3	11.1	73.2
9	M3		68.3	8.3	20.4	68.1	8.1	20.2	68.2	8.2	20.3	68.2	8.2	20.3	71.6

Note: A = Acetone, E= Ethanol, M= Methanol, nm = no mordant, L = whiteness to blackness, a = greenness to redness, b = blueness to yellowness, L_{nm}= whiteness to blackness no mordant, a_{nm}= greenness to redness no mordant, b_{nm}= blueness to yellowness no mordant, ΔE_{nm}= Delta E no mordant

Table 6. Color Parameters Value for Wash Fastness of Dyed Cotton Fabric Mordanted with Alum

S/N	Solvent	Wash fastness Image	L ₁	a ₁	b ₁	L ₂	a ₂	b ₂	L ₃	a ₃	b ₃	L _{al}	a _{al}	b _{al}	ΔE _{al}
1	A1		59.3	11.4	22.1	59.1	11.4	22.1	59.2	11.3	22.0	59.2	11.3	22.0	64.2
2	E1		63.0	0.6	22.0	62.9	0.5	21.9	63.1	0.7	22.1	63.0	0.6	22.0	66.7
3	M1		77.0	-2.1	2.0	77.1	-2.2	2.1	76.9	-2.0	1.9	77.0	-2.1	2.0	77.1
4	A2		59.5	11.6	22.2	59.3	11.4	22.0	59.4	11.5	22.1	59.4	11.5	22.1	64.4
5	E2		63.1	0.8	22.1	63.0	0.7	22.0	63.2	0.9	22.2	63.1	0.8	22.1	66.9
6	M2		77.3	-2.2	2.3	77.1	-2.0	2.1	77.2	-2.1	2.2	77.2	-2.1	2.2	77.3
7	A3		59.6	11.7	22.3	59.5	11.6	22.2	59.4	11.5	22.1	59.5	11.6	22.2	64.6
8	E3		63.2	1.0	22.0	63.1	0.9	21.9	63.3	1.1	22.1	63.2	1.0	22.0	66.9
9	M3		77.4	-2.1	2.2	77.2	-1.9	2.0	77.3	-2.0	2.1	77.3	-2.0	2.1	77.4

Note: A = Acetone, E= Ethanol, M= Methanol, nm = no mordant, L = whiteness to blackness, a = greenness to redness, b = blueness to yellowness, L_{nm}= whiteness to blackness no mordant, a_{nm}= greenness to redness no mordant, b_{nm}= blueness to yellowness no mordant, ΔE_{nm}= Delta E no mordant